

Divergence between Perceived and Desired Criteria for Assessing Researchers

Results from a 2025 Cross-Center Survey at the Helmholtz Association

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Abstract

The Helmholtz Open Science Office (OS Office) is the central hub for open science within the Helmholtz Association, Germany's largest scientific organization with 18 research centers across six research areas. It contributes to national and international open science developments and guides reforms in research assessment. In February 2025, the OS Office signed the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA) and joined the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA), reflecting its commitment to responsible, quality-oriented evaluation practices.

To support research assessment reforms across the 18 Helmholtz Research Centers, the OS Office and the Helmholtz Working Group Open Science established the cross-cutting Helmholtz Task Group Research Assessment in March 2025. This bottom-up initiative aims to inform researchers and management about national and international developments in the fields of research assessment and evaluation, increase the visibility of ongoing research assessment reform efforts within the Helmholtz Association, and provide a platform for identifying and developing new quality-oriented research assessment systems and tools. To support these goals with an empirical evidence base, the Task Group conducted a short cross-center survey among Helmholtz researchers and research-related staff.

The purpose of the survey was twofold: first, to understand which criteria researchers perceive as currently shaping performance evaluations and career decisions; and second, to identify which criteria they believe should be considered in the future. The survey was conducted from June 23, 2025 to September 23, 2025 as an anonymous online questionnaire targeting all 18 Helmholtz Centers and covering all six research areas. In total, 1,145 responses were collected.

The survey reveals a broad consensus on the need to reform towards more value-based evaluation criteria as well as important disciplinary and role-based differences across professional positions. The data provides an empirical basis for developing modular CV formats, revised evaluation guidelines, and center-level implementation strategies. More broadly, it contributes to the international discourse on reforming research assessment by offering large-scale, institutionally grounded evidence from a major research organization.

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1 Background

1.1 Institutional Context

The Helmholtz Association is Germany's largest scientific organization, bringing together 18 independent research centers that address major societal challenges across six research areas: Health; Earth and Environment; Energy; Information; Aeronautics, Space and Transport; and Matter. With its mission-oriented structure and strong emphasis on long-term research programs, Helmholtz operates at the intersection of basic research, infrastructure provision, and societal application. The Helmholtz Association monitors its research programs within the 7-year Program-Oriented Funding (PoF) cycle using a set of 13 numerical indicators as well as narrative descriptions in annual reports. Each center's management has autonomy to set criteria for the hiring and assessing of individual researchers (in accordance with good scientific practices).

The [Helmholtz Open Science Office](#) (OS Office) is a central coordination and competence hub for open science within the Helmholtz Association and an active contributor to national and international open science efforts. The open science movement and research assessment reforms share many common goals, above all the aim of enhancing research quality, impact, and trustworthiness. By recognizing a broader range of research outputs and activities, the visibility and influence of research can be strengthened, while also giving greater acknowledgment to different contributions of researchers and supporting staff. In this context, the OS Office guides the ongoing efforts to reform research assessment practices and criteria aligned with the Helmholtz Open Science Policy¹ and the interests of the Helmholtz Association.

The Association's reform activities are embedded in a broader policy landscape. The Helmholtz Open Science Office is an active member of the [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment](#) (CoARA) and has recently reaffirmed its commitment to reforming research assessment in its CoARA Action Plan². This Action Plan outlines the OS Office's role in fostering the openness, quality, and impact of research within the Helmholtz Association while shaping enabling framework conditions. It maps open science-research assessment synergies, the current status quo, and planned 2026-2030 activities tied to CoARA's commitments.

¹ Helmholtz-Gemeinschaft (Ed.) (2022): Helmholtz Open Science Policy. Version 1.0. Approved in the 119th General Assembly of the Helmholtz Association on 20-21 September 2022, Helmholtz-Gemeinschaft, 9 p. <https://doi.org/10.48440/os.helmholtz.056>

² Helmholtz Open Science Office. (2026). CoARA Action Plan by the Helmholtz Open Science Office. Helmholtz Open Science Office. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18242817>

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In March 2025, to increase awareness and knowledge exchange around research assessment reforms and to support and guide the Helmholtz Research Centers in further development of quality-oriented evaluation approaches and criteria, OS Office and the [Helmholtz Working Group Open Science](#) launched a cross-cutting [Helmholtz Task Group Research Assessment](#). This group brings together experts from the Helmholtz Research Centers with diverse expertise (libraries, open science, strategy, HR, equal opportunities, funding, postdoc and PhD representatives).

This Task Group provides a bottom-up initiative within the Helmholtz Association that aims to (1) inform Helmholtz researchers and management on ongoing national and international developments in research assessment, (2) improve the visibility of (research assessment) reform initiatives taking place within the Helmholtz Association (3) provide a platform for identifying and developing new quality-oriented research assessment systems and tools.

1.2 Motivation

The need for reform arises from growing recognition that traditional evaluation systems, often centered on journal-based metrics such as impact factors, publication counts, and citation numbers, capture only a limited spectrum of scholarly contributions. While such indicators may provide partial information about visibility and productivity, they frequently fail to account for the quality, complexity, and diversity of contemporary research work. For example, important scholarly outputs, such as datasets, software, and methodological publications, currently receive insufficient recognition. Equally overlooked are contributions like mentoring, supervision, data stewardship, software development, infrastructure management, interdisciplinary collaboration, and engagement with societal stakeholders.

It is important to recognize that there is no one-size-fits-all solution to research assessment. Differences across disciplines, research cultures, organizational structures, and types of scholarly work mean that assessment frameworks must be flexible and context-sensitive. Assessment criteria that are appropriate for one field or institution may be less relevant, or even counterproductive, in another. Effective reform therefore requires tailored approaches that reflect the diverse ways in which research is conducted, shared, and applied, while ensuring fairness, transparency, broad recognition of contributions, and consideration of relevant professional and personal circumstances.

1.3 Objectives of the Survey

The survey was designed to address two central questions. First, which criteria do researchers in the 18 Helmholtz Research Centers believe are currently used to assess their performance and influence career progression? This question targets perceived institutional reality and provides insight into the implicit incentive structures shaping research behavior.

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Second, which criteria do researchers believe should be considered in the future? This question captures normative expectations and reform aspirations within the community.

By directly comparing perceived and desired criteria, the survey enables identification of alignment or misalignment between existing evaluation cultures and researchers' preferences. Furthermore, by collecting background information on career stage and research area, the survey allows exploration of whether expectations differ systematically across disciplines or career roles. The criteria set was adapted from a recent international analysis of academic promotion practices to reflect the specific characteristics of the Helmholtz research environments.

2 Methodology

The survey was designed to be brief to minimize the time commitment for respondents (average 8'46", median 6'23") and maximize participation. It survey was implemented as an anonymous online questionnaire, open from June 23, 2025 to September 23, 2025.

Researchers and research-related staff at the 18 Helmholtz Centers were invited to participate via internal communication channels (institutional and thematic mailing lists). Participation was voluntary. With over 29,000 researchers and research-related staff across Helmholtz Association, the 1,145 responses represent a self-selected sample rather than a statistically representative sample of the entire population.

Evaluation criteria - The questionnaire presented a comprehensive list of 40 evaluation criteria, spanning traditional metric-based indicators as well as qualitative and contribution-oriented measures. The original list of criteria was adapted from Lim et al. (2025)³ and adapted by the Helmholtz Task Group Research Assessment to reflect Helmholtz-specific institutional profiles and priorities. Criteria included: Administrative roles, Advisory role to policymakers, Authorship order/position, Awards, Collaborations, Commercialization and consultancy, Communication and outreach, Conference attendance, Conference organization, Contributions to a healthy institutional culture, Contributions to equity/diversity/inclusivity, Contributions to peer review, Developing/maintaining digital infrastructures and software, Developing/operating research facilities and instruments, Editorial roles, Ethics and integrity, Far-sight, Funding, Interdisciplinarity, Internationalization, Invited positions, Journal impact factor, Memberships in committees/boards etc., Mentoring, Non-metric journal quality, Non-metric quality of publications, Non-text publications (data/software/methods/etc.), Number of citations, Number of co-authors, Number of publications, Number of recent publications, Open Science practices, Patents, Presentations, Professional development, Professional titles, Role of authors, Societal impact, Supervision, and Teaching.

³ Lim, B.H., D'Ippoliti, C., Dominik, M. et al. Regional and institutional trends in assessment for academic promotion. *Nature* 638, 459-468 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-024-08422-9>

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The 40 criteria were presented to respondents in alphabetical order and they were asked to select and rank their top ten criteria in response to two separate questions:

- Which of the following criteria do you believe **are used** to assess or value your performance, for example when applying for a permanent position or promotion?
- Which of the following criteria do you believe **should be used** to assess or value your performance, for example when applying for a permanent position or promotion?

Respondent background – Respondents reported their career stages according to the European Framework for Research Careers⁴, including first-stage, recognized, established, and leading researchers, as well as department heads, and institute directors. An additional category for technical or infrastructure staff was added. Of 1,145 completed responses, covering all six Helmholtz research areas, participants reported their primary research area (Energy, Earth and Environment, Health, Information, Matter, or Aeronautics, Space and Transport) and their employing Helmholtz Center. Center-level data remains confidential for internal use. No personal identifiers were collected; the survey complied with GDPR and institutional data protection standards.

Data processing – To enable comparisons across research areas and career stages, survey data was processed as follows: Respondents ranked their top ten evaluation criteria (1 = most important, 10 = least important). Ranks were converted into points and scored inversely, with the first rank receiving 10 points, 9 points for the second, down to 1 point for the 10th rank. Points were then summed across all respondents to calculate weighted scores per criterion. Selection frequency was tracked separately.

3 Data Description

The dataset can be found here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18944700>

Sheet 1 provides all original data at the individual response level (one row per completed questionnaire). Variables include career stage, research area, and ranked positions (1-10) for each selected criterion in both the perceived relevance (“used”) and desired relevance (“should”) questions.

Sheet 2 presents weighted and normalized data (see Methodology) for perceived (“used”, columns B-E) and desired (“should”, columns F-I) evaluation criteria across the entire cohort. Frequency (columns B and F) indicates how often each criterion appeared in participants’ top-10 rankings. Weighted scores (columns C and G) convert these frequencies into points according to their position within the top-10 rankings. Rankings (columns D and H) order the

⁴ European Commission (2011), “Towards a European Framework for Research Careers”: <https://circabc.europa.eu/sd/a/d1ae7fdd-e80f-4b54-973b-dcea380132e4/ED-20120315-WG3-Point%203-Framework%20Research%20Careers-short.pdf>

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criteria from highest to lowest weighted score. Subsequent sheets present the same data stratified by specific career stages and research areas.

4 Results

4.1 Figures and Aggregated Results

The overall distribution of the 1,145 completed responses shows broad participation across research areas and career stages, with particularly strong representation from the Health and Earth & Environment areas (Figure 1). Furthermore, participation from all different career stages enables meaningful cross-stage comparisons (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Distribution of responses by career stage and research area.

When comparing perceived and desired evaluation criteria, a clear divergence becomes visible (Figure 2). Traditional quantitative output-based indicators (such as publication counts, citation numbers, and journal-based metrics) are widely perceived as influential in current evaluation practices. In contrast, when asked which criteria should shape future evaluations, respondents prioritize a broader, more value-based set of contributions. Frequently highlighted desired criteria include collaborations, supervision and mentoring, professional development, ethics and integrity, contributions to a healthy institutional culture, interdisciplinarity, societal impact, and non-metric assessments of publication quality.

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Figure 2: Comparison of perceived current assessment criteria and desired assessment criteria.

Differences in desired criteria across research areas suggest disciplinary context matters (Figure 3). For example, infrastructure-related contributions rank higher in Earth & Environment research area, while Health researchers emphasize ethics and integrity, as well as contributions to a healthy institutional culture. Similarly, career-stage comparisons indicate role-based dynamics: early-career researchers prioritize institutional culture and integrity-related aspects, whereas senior researchers more frequently highlight output-based criteria (Figure 4).

Figure 3: Comparison of desired assessment criteria between Health and Earth & Environment research areas.

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Figure 4: Comparison of desired assessment criteria between leading researchers and early career researchers.

5 Limitations

Several factors warrant consideration when interpreting the survey findings.

Recruitment and coverage bias: The survey relied on multipliers (e.g., institutional contacts) and topical mailing lists to reach potential respondents. This approach likely influenced who received invitations and ultimately who participated. Consequently, some centers and research areas achieved good coverage, while some remain underrepresented.

Participation bias: Participation was voluntary, and respondents were likely those with a particular interest in research assessment and its reforms. Individuals less engaged with, or concerned about, assessment practices may be underrepresented. Thus, the survey may overrepresent critics of the current system motivated to advocate for change, potentially skewing perceived priorities and normative preferences.

Self-reported perceptions versus formal criteria: The survey captures respondents' self-reported perceptions of current evaluation practices. These may not align fully with formal institutional criteria. Such views may reflect personal experiences, expectations, or assumptions rather than official procedures.

Top-10 ranking format: Respondents ranked their top-10 evaluation criteria. While this effectively highlights relative priorities, it may underrepresent criteria deemed important but not top-ranked. Less frequently selected criteria may still hold substantial significance for specific groups but appear less prominently in the aggregated data.

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7 Citation and License

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